

An Empirical Analysis of Student's Factors on Students' Mathematics Performance of Grade 7 Students

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to match the different learning factors on the Mathematics Performance of the Grade 7 Students of University of Cebu, SY 2023 – 2024 as basis for effectiveness in learning Secondary Mathematics. This study employed a descriptive comparative using t-test for Independent Samples from 2 independent samples namely, Grade 7 Love and Grade 7 Peace, and after the processing, interpretation, and analysis of data, the action plan was created. This design enables to examine whether significant differences exist among the Demographic Profile and Academic Performance, in terms of the predictor variables, by extension, the

accuracy of the classification. This design enables to deepen the teaching skills of the teachers by giving themselves a time to adjust their expertise to the students with these kinds of discipline. The respondents were already grouped accordingly. A focus group discussion was done to elicit the highlights and lowlights of the study. The student's related factor is one of the important aspects of high fail rate in mathematics that plays a vital role in a teaching learning process. Without students' interest in the teaching learning activities there is no possibility to achieve knowledge in subject matter. Student's achievement depends on their need, interest, practices, and seriousness in subject matter. Students related factors include mathematics anxiety, prior knowledge of students and student's labor in learning mathematics. The result of the study reveals that that there is a significant difference between its demographic profile and academic performance in mathematics on the study habits, learning problem, and mathematics anxiety. Moreover, it found out also that there is no significant difference between its demographic profile and academic performance in mathematics on the teacher relations, parental attitudes, and learning environment with the discriminant analysis. It is highly recommended that they can utilize Learning Enhancement Programs such as peer mentoring, cooperative learning activities, scaffolding, remediation activities, and other supplementary seminars or webinars that enhance the students' skills in learning mathematics. By this, it will allow the students to be the center of the teaching – learning process so that the low performing students can adopt to the modification of the learning process.

Keywords: *mathematics performance, student factors, study habits, mathematics anxiety, learning problems, grade 7 students, mathematics enhancement plan*

INTRODUCTION

Instructional design is an effective means of alleviating many pressing problems in education. It is an authoritative discipline, a body of knowledge that prescribes instructional actions to enhance desired educational results, such as success and impact on performance. This research was chosen so that the mathematics teachers will become aware of the academic factors that affect the relationship between the students' factors in learning mathematics because most of them got low scores without considering the factors that contribute. The paper seeks to analyze some factors affecting students' mathematics performance at the University of Cebu. After teaching mathematics for 5 years at the university, most of the problems that existed were the difficulty of the terminologies and the process itself of how certain solutions and concepts were derived and tackled. Tutorials and other sorts of academic help helped a lot in making learning possible. In this research, we found out the factors that existed in the failure of the respondents in mathematics—not just failing but rather the difficulty of the subject matter. It is therefore an irrefutable fact that the success of learning the subject is contingent on a myriad of reasons. School, student, and teacher factors all impinge on the learning of mathematics. Educators, trainers, and researchers have long been interested in exploring the reasons that effectively contribute to the quality of student achievement. Students envisioned their 'use' of knowledge in daily scenarios, in contrast to their teachers' goals of fostering learners' academic performances (Zhou, Jiming, Zhao, et. al., 2019).

The researcher observed that students are having difficulty with their art of critical thinking and that there may be a lack of comprehension given the mode of learning. Module design, nature of assessment, and submissions delimit the scope of this study. This research evaluates their academic performances in mathematics and gives an analysis of effectiveness in learning mathematics as part of human exploration.

This paper recommends a solution to solve the gap in the difficulty of the art of critical thinking through conducting enhancement programs that allow the students to engage and apprehend mathematics in reality. These enhancement activities may include webinars and seminars, transfer tasks, mathematics tutorials, and enhancement conferences such as seminar workshops.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to match the different learning factors on the Mathematics Performance of the Grade 7 Students of the University of Cebu, SY 2023 – 2024 as basis for effectiveness in learning Secondary Mathematics. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the university students with regard to:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. family income; and
 - 1.4. parent's educational qualifications

2. What is the status of the high-performing and low-performing students in mathematics with regard to:
 - 2.1. study habits;
 - 2.2. learning problem;
 - 2.3. mathematics anxiety;
 - 2.4. teacher relationship; and
 - 2.5. parents attitudes towards mathematics;

2.6. learning environment

3. Is there a significant difference between its high and low performing students in Mathematics on the six variables?
4. Which factors can discriminate the students Mathematics Performance?
5. What Mathematics Enhancement Activities can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Conceptual mathematical understanding is knowledge that involves a deep understanding of the underlying and fundamental concepts behind the algorithms performed in mathematics. This refers to a situation in which students can make decisions and apply their knowledge through active engagement. A student must have both knowledge to understand mathematics thoroughly. Teachers will be more confident in recognizing when students are prepared for standards-based tests and can demonstrate a real understanding of concepts. They should be intrigued about the relationship between concepts in mathematics and learning (Andamon & Tan, 2018).

Researchers have found that several teachers have difficulty teaching problem-solving in their classrooms. Teachers' lack of knowledge could affect their teaching performance in problem-solving activities. Understanding teachers' SMK and PCK could in relation to problem posing could have far reaching and lasting implications in the assessment and improvement of their teacher knowledge, thereby improving the problem posing and overall mathematical performance of their students as well (Lee & Capraro, 2018).

The social learning theory emphasizes human behavior based on a continuous mutual interaction between cognitive, behavioral, and environmental influences. The component processes underlying observational learning are attention, including modeled events distinctiveness, affective valence, complexity, prevalence, functional value) and observer characteristics (sensory capacities, arousal level, perceptual set, past reinforcement), retention, including symbolic coding, cognitive organization, symbolic rehearsal, motor rehearsal), motor reproduction, including physical capabilities, self-observation of reproduction, accuracy of feedback, and motivation, including external, vicarious, and self-reinforcement (Acharya, 2017).

The determining factors of students' academic performance include class participation, class assignments, homework, examinations, quizzes, and participation in competitions or other events. Pressure from parents and others on teachers and school administrators has enabled schools to develop progressive strategies. These include encouraging additional courses for students, adopting effective teaching, and learning methods and instructional strategies, using technology, rewarding students for good performance which serves as a motivating factor and when they get poor grades, they generally tend to work harder to improve. When teachers implement the strategies to reward good performance, they become motivated to learn and improve their academic performance. Secondary school students usually belonging to upper class and wealthy families are aware and aspire to have a good career (Kapur, 2018).

Mathematics teachers face the daunting task of creating a constructivist learning environment while considering the learning style preferences of the students in the classroom. The Dunn and Dunn model is one of the most influential learning style models developed. According to Dunn, a learning style is

characterized by how a student begins to focus on, manage, internalize, and remember new material. The interaction of these elements occurs differently in each person and can vary according to gender, age, and culture. The Dunn and Dunn's model consist of five learning styles stimuli and several elements in each stimulus. These are as follows: environmental (sound, light, temperature, and spatial layout); emotional (motivation, persistence, responsibility, and structure); sociological (learning alone, in pairs, with classmates, with a teacher and mixed); physiological (perceptual intake during learning, chronological energy pattern, and mobility needs); and psychological processing (impulsive or reflective, and global or analytical). The teachers may have little power over some of these elements in the classroom, apart from sound, individual versus group learning, as well as learner mobility - which relate to the kinesthetic, individual, and group-learning styles (Schulze & Bosman, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the method used in this study. Specifically, the following are included: research design, respondents, instruments, data gathering procedures, data analysis, and ethical considerations.

Participants

The respondents were the grade 7 students who were selected as participants of this study. They were selected based on the first quarter grades given on October 21, 2023. Low-performing students are coming from Grade 7 Peace since they have low scores in the said exam, while high-performing students are coming from Grade 7 Love since they have high scores in the said exam. Regrouping was not possible since it was already established, and the students were 50 per class. There were 100 students in total, with ages ranging mostly from 12 to 13 years old.

Instrument

A standardized questionnaire comprises into two types, namely: (1) the demographic profile of the respondents, and (2) the academic performance in mathematics of the respondents. This was used to determine the performance of grade 7 students in mathematics.

To determine parental responses and student perceptions regarding their children's mathematics performance. Parents answered each question in a 5-point Likert format: "Strongly Disagree," "Disagree," "Neutral," "Agree," and "Strongly Agree." The results were identified using the weighted mean statistical tool as a 5-point Likert scale from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

Data Gathering Procedure

Pre-Data Gathering. The researcher sent a letter to the Principal of the Basic Education Department requesting permission to conduct the study. The researcher also wrote a letter to the teacher – adviser, informing them that the selected students were the respondents to this study. After that, the paper was also submitted to the Institution Review Board (IRB) to obtain a certificate of notice to proceed.

Actual data gathering. On the day of the data gathering, the researcher will once again explain the purpose and mechanics of the survey so that the respondents will have an idea about it, and then administer the standardized questionnaires. The teachers will also pinpoint at least an idea of the reason(s)

the research was conducted in their classes. Hence, the data on the performance evaluation of the respondents was taken through a standardized questionnaire, including the qualitative data coming from their teachers. Another survey will also be given to the parents through the students telling the same mechanics as mentioned in the class.

Post: Data Gathering. The data gathered were collected, tallied, tabulated, and statistically treated using t-test to test the significant difference and the identified factors in the study. Data analysis followed.

Data Analysis

To know the students' level based on their demographic profile, their status in mathematics, and the parent's responses to the attitude and perceptions of the students toward mathematics.

To determine the differences between the high- and low-performing students, the t-test of an independent sample was used.

To know the highlights and lowlights of the study, the students' responses and parents' responses were collected and tabulated, and then a thematic analysis was done. The responses and data collected were categorized and identified, and a report was made.

A relevant proposal was made based on the findings of this study.

Ethical Considerations

The services of the Institutional Ethics Review Board of Cebu Normal University were utilized. The Institutional Review Board essentially allowed third parties unknown to the researcher to review ethical considerations based on beneficence, respect, and justice. In conducting research, ethical consideration was given importance to protect the validity, dignity, and safety of the research participants to strengthen its quality standards. Several ethical considerations were considered to ensure that the study was conducted in an appropriate manner (Babbie & Mouton, 2001). In compliance with ethical considerations in conducting research to all participants. Written consent was provided to the participants in the conduct of the research study and secured accordingly, and make sure that only those who were permitted to join the conduct of this study were included in the teaching – learning process for this purpose.

Thus, the researcher explained the purpose in conducting this research to the respondents and asked for their honest answers to ensure the success of the study. Respondents were informed ahead of time. All participants used the same questionnaires. Their participation was their generous contribution to the success of the study. Appreciation through words of thanks as driving force for accomplishing the questionnaire was extended by the researcher to the respondents.

Finally, with all the guidelines prescribed by the University, all requirements were fully accomplished before the conduct of the study. Ethical review and approval by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the University Ethics Committee was sought. Thus, the principles and standards of the report supported the conduct of this study.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings and analysis of the data gathered from the Students' Mathematics Performance Survey. A total of 100 respondents from 50 Low Performing Students and 50 High Performing Students provided the data for analysis. The data were treated using the SPSS Version 23.

Personal Background

Personal Background included in this study were the following: (1) Age; (2) Gender; (3) Family Gross Monthly Income; and (4) Parents' Qualifications.

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age Bracket	f	%
12 – 13	90	90.00
14 – 15	10	10.00
Sex		
Female	78	78.00
Male	22	22.00
Family Gross Monthly Income		
Between P11,690.00 - P23,381.00	32	32.00
Between P23,381.00 - P46,761.00	16	16.00
Between P46,761.00 - P81,832.00	14	14.00
Less than P11,690.00	38	38.00
Parents' Qualification		
Basic Education	37	37.00
Postgraduate Studies	10	10.00
Undergraduate Degrees	47	47.00
Vocational Courses	6	60.00

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents who answered the standardized questionnaire, with 100 respondents from the low- and high-performing classes. It identified that between the ages of 12 and 13 years old, about 90% of the respondents answered the survey, and about 10% of the respondents between the ages of 14 and 15 years old answered the survey. Moreover, about 78% of the respondents are female, and about 22% are male. Regarding the family gross monthly income of the respondents, there are about 32% of the respondents with a monthly gross family income of between P11,690.00 and P23,381.00; about 16% of the respondents with a monthly gross family income of between P23,381.00 and P46,761.00; about 14% of the respondents with a monthly gross family income of between P46,761.00 and P81,832.00; and about 38% of the respondents with a monthly gross family income of less than P11,690.00. For the parents' qualifications of the respondents, there are about 37% who finished basic education alone; about 10% of the respondents who finished their postgraduate studies; about 47% of the respondents finished their undergraduate studies; and about 60% of the respondents finished the vocational courses.

Dela Cruz (2017) stated that Asians are often stereotyped as good problem solvers, but Filipino students seem to have difficulty learning and solving mathematics problems. The Trends in Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) current result was that the Philippines had been outsmarted by our neighboring Asian countries that got the highest ranks. According to Jalmasco (2014), even though the science high schools in the country participated in the Advanced Mathematics Category, the Philippines still ranked lowest among the 10 countries. This implies that Filipino students and teachers need to go hand in hand to develop higher cognitive demands. This shows that students need to improve their critical and analytical thinking skills to improve their academic performance and be globally competitive. Furthermore, the data shown in the table was the result of the intensive analysis of the college students who reviewed the study.

Status of the Respondents in Mathematics

The majority of the respondents are female and between the ages of 12 and 13 years old. The basis of the status of the respondents as low- and high-performing classes is the results of the first quarter. In the succeeding presentations, it was found that the high-performing class had a better mean result compared with the low-performing class in terms of study habits, learning problems, mathematics anxiety, teacher relationships, parents' attitudes, and learning environment.

Study Habits of the Students in Mathematics

Mathematical concepts mostly involve computations and problem-solving, which need to be practiced by the students not only in school but also at home. For this reason, teachers often give students tasks to practice skills. However, if students are busy with other activities, they have limited or no time to practice the skills they are learning.

Table 2
Study Habits of the Students in Mathematics

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
I only study during exam days/weeks.	3.94	1.00	A	4.36	0.88	SA
I study every day.	4.14	1.28	A	4.30	1.13	SA
I study monthly.	3.92	0.90	A	1.86	0.97	D
I study in case of emergency.	3.66	1.10	A	1.64	0.90	SD
I do not study.	3.16	1.28	N	1.46	0.86	SD
I do my assignments regularly.	3.62	0.99	A	4.60	0.76	SA
I exert more effort when I do difficult assignment.	3.18	1.24	N	4.32	0.89	SA
I spend my vacant time in doing assignments or studying my lesson.	3.30	1.05	N	3.94	0.98	A
I study the lessons I missed if I was absent from the class.	3.06	1.06	N	4.48	0.65	SA
I study and prepare for the quizzes and tests.	3.66	0.69	A	4.66	0.48	SA
I study harder to improve my performance when I get low scores.	3.38	0.99	N	4.58	0.61	SA

During school time, I spend less time with friends to concentrate more on my studies.	3.20	1.28	N	4.32	0.91	SA
I prefer to finish my studies and homework first before watching any TV shows etc.	3.28	1.25	N	4.22	0.84	SA
I see to it that extracurricular activities do not hamper my studies.	3.14	1.25	N	4.44	0.70	SA
I have specific place of study at home which I remain clean and orderly.	3.58	0.84	A	4.26	1.14	SA
Factor Mean	3.05	1.08	Satisfactory	4.17	0.85	Very Satisfactory

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree (SD); 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree (D); 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral (N); 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree (A); and 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree (SA).

This part shows the results of the respondents in mathematics. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.05 for the low-performing class and about 4.17 for the high-performing class, with an overall standard deviation of 1.08 for the low-performing class and about 0.85 for the high-performing class. This means that the respondents were interpreted as satisfactory in the low-performing class and very satisfactory in the high-performing class. The data suggests that the respondents' study habits improved more in the high performing class. Given the nature of their study habits, this can be considered one of the reasons for their high mathematics performance.

Sakirudeen and Sanni (2017) found that study habits such as note-taking, library usage, and allocation of study time influenced students' academic performance. They also recommended organizing group counseling sessions in schools initiated by school guidance counselors to create awareness about practical study habits and the provision of a functional library in secondary schools, which could lead to better student performance in mathematics.

Learning Problems of the Students in Mathematics

The nature of the learning problem can be considered one of the reasons for the moderate mathematics performance of the high performing class. In any academic activity, intrinsic mechanisms play a crucial role in the learning process. In mathematics, in particular, students' academic performance is strongly influenced by their drive and motivation to learn the subject. Intrinsic motivation is categorized by students' awareness of the learning process and their satisfaction with it. This concept sheds light on how students' drive to excel in mathematics is closely linked to their academic achievements (Martin & Marsh, 2021).

Table 3
Learning Problems of the Students in Mathematics

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
Lack of Study Habits	3.34	0.92	N	4.18	0.63	A
Teacher Factor	3.10	1.22	N	2.64	0.66	N
I hate Math	2.90	1.16	N	2.72	0.78	N

Peer Pressure	3.32	1.27	N	3.64	0.72	A
Family Problem	3.32	1.02	N	3.28	1.01	N
I can acquire what is being imparted in class this year.	3.68	0.94	A	4.60	0.57	SA
I can solve anything if I try hard enough.	3.54	1.11	A	4.06	0.55	A
If I practiced every day, I could develop almost any skill.	3.44	0.95	A	4.30	0.54	SA
Once I have decided to achieve something that is important to me, I keep trying to achieve it, even if it is harder than I thought.	3.74	0.88	A	3.84	0.74	A
I am assured that I will accomplish the areas that I set for myself.	3.56	0.91	A	3.88	0.87	A
Factor Mean	3.20	1.04	High	3.42	0.71	Moderate

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree or Very High; 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree or High; 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral or Moderate; 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree or Low; 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree or Very Low.

This part shows the results of the respondents' learning problems in mathematics. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.20 for the low-performing class and about 3.42 for the high-performing class, with an overall standard deviation of 1.04 for the low performing class and about 0.71 for the high-performing class. This means that the respondents interpreted the learning problem as high for the low-performing class and moderate for the high-performing class. The data suggests that the learning problems of the respondents in the low-performing class need to be improved as compared with the high-performing class. Given the nature of the learning problem, this can be considered one of the reasons for the moderate mathematics achievements of the high-performing class.

Batool (2019) found that students who performed well academically were more likely to achieve the objectives of the curriculum compared to those who did not perform well. Similarly, Okwelle (2020) found that students who performed poorly academically had a lower likelihood of achieving the intended learning outcomes of the curriculum. These suggest that mathematics performance is a key predictor of curriculum effectiveness.

Mathematics Anxiety of the Students

The students articulated that mathematics is important in their lives as they can smear these concepts in some of their regular actions. However, these positive thoughts still need to be improved to make them understand that, regardless of the situation of the person, mathematics is valuable no matter what the person's status in life is. Therefore, learning mathematics is important, as it is one of the necessary skills that everyone needs in their life now and in the future.

Table 4
Mathematics Anxiety of the Students

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
I prepare for mathematics.	3.60	0.88	A	4.32	0.51	SA

I listen carefully to my mathematics teacher's lectures.	3.40	0.95	N	4.34	0.66	SA
I actively participate in discussions, answering exercises and/or clarify things that I have not understand.	3.70	0.81	A	4.10	0.81	A
I want to get good grades in exams, tests, assignments and projects.	3.76	0.87	A	4.28	0.90	SA
I get frustrated when the discussion is interrupted.	3.46	0.86	A	4.06	0.84	A
I think hard work pays off.	3.44	0.97	A	3.98	0.87	A
My abilities grow with effort.	3.46	1.01	A	4.06	1.06	A
I be certain of that the intellect can be established like a muscle.	3.54	0.89	A	4.02	0.91	A
I believe that you can significantly change.	3.86	0.67	A	3.84	0.89	A
I can significantly change my base skill level.	3.80	0.64	A	3.92	0.92	A
Factor Mean	3.60	0.86	Low	4.09	0.84	Low

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree or Very High; 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree or High; 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral or Moderate; 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree or Low; and 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree or Very Low.

This part displays the outcomes of the mathematics anxiety of the respondents. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.60 for the low-performing class and about 4.09 for the high-performing class, with an overall standard deviation of 0.86 for the low-performing class and about 0.84 for the high-performing class. This means that the respondents interpreted the mathematics anxiety of the low- and high-performing classes as low. The data suggests that the mathematics anxiety of the respondents needs to be improved for the low- and high-performing classes. Given the nature of mathematics anxiety, it can be considered one of the reasons for the poor mathematics performance of the respondents.

Disregarding this level of anxiety among the students when learning mathematics could have a bad impact on their performance. Therefore, educators need to find strategies to improve the confidence of students in learning mathematics. In the study of Mohamed and Waheed (2018) on secondary students who were asked to answer a questionnaire regarding the students' confidence in math and its usefulness, they found that there was a moderately positive attitude of the respondents towards mathematics. Evaluate the perception of respondents about the value of mathematics in their lives, showing their anxiety about the subject.

Teacher Relationship with the Students in Mathematics

The relationship between the teacher and the student is very important for the student's success in math. A positive and supportive relationship can help with math anxiety, boost engagement, and get students to take an active role in their learning. When teachers show empathy and build trust, students become more confident and better at math. This study looks at how the relationships between teachers and students affect how motivated and successful students are in math.

Table 5
Teacher Relationship of the Students in Mathematics

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
My teacher has a good relationship with the students and co-teachers.	3.94	0.68	A	4.26	0.53	SA
My teacher shows smartness, confidence and firmness in making decisions regarding mathematics.	4.02	0.77	A	4.14	0.70	A
My teacher Imposes proper discipline and is not lenient in following the prescribed rules.	2.08	0.97	D	1.92	0.70	D
My teacher has an appealing personality and has a good sense of humor.	4.22	0.51	SA	4.26	0.44	SA
My teacher is open to suggestions and opinions and is worthy of praise.	3.84	0.77	A	4.00	0.57	A
My teacher explains the objectives of the lesson clearly at the start of the lesson.	3.74	0.80	A	3.88	0.66	A
My teacher has mastery of the subject matter.	4.22	0.51	SA	4.28	0.45	SA
My teacher is organized in presenting the lessons by systematically following the course outline.	4.26	0.44	SA	4.30	0.46	SA
My teacher is updated with the present trends, relevant to the subject matter.	4.12	0.63	A	4.18	0.63	A
My teacher uses various strategies, teaching aids/devices and techniques in presenting the lessons.	4.04	0.70	A	4.10	0.71	A
My teacher provides support for all students.	4.34	0.48	SA	4.42	0.50	SA
My teacher has a positive attitude daily.	4.20	0.40	A	4.34	0.48	SA
My teacher presents the information in a way that is easy to understand.	4.14	0.61	A	4.30	0.54	SA
My teacher cares about my academic and social well – being.	4.10	0.68	A	4.28	0.57	SA
My teacher is sensitive to all students.	4.10	0.58	A	4.10	0.71	A
Factor Mean	3.96	0.63	Positive	4.05	0.58	Positive

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree or Very Negative; 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree or Negative; 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral and Moderately Positive; 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree or Positive; and 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree or Very Positive.

This part presents the results of the teacher-student relationship among the respondents in the subject of mathematics. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.96 in the low- performing class and about 4.05 in the high-performing class, with an overall standard deviation of 0.63 in the low-performing class and about 0.58 in the high-performing class. This means that the respondents interpreted the teacher relationship as positive for both low- and high-performing classes. The data suggests that the teacher-student relationship somehow improved for the low- and high-performing classes. One of the reasons for this can be considered to be the nature of the teacher-student relationship among the respondents' best performers in mathematics.

Our results showed that the effects of the respondents' relationship with teachers in mathematics were mediated by mathematics achievement. Regarding the role of self-esteem, the non-significant indirect effects on mathematics achievement were consistent with other studies. When analyzing the presentation, both the low- and high-performing classes are positive. This effect could be interpreted in light of the relationship between self-esteem and the quality of the student-teacher relationship.

The data analysis showed a strong relationship between these measures. Therefore, the quality of the teacher-student relationship explains the large influence of teachers of mathematics' instruction. Students who are trusted can excel in mathematics, as recommended and demonstrated by several scholars. Callaman and Itaas (2020) reported that the teacher-student relationship is academically connected with academic achievement in the mathematics examination. The beliefs students develop about their mathematical abilities help regulate what they do with the knowledge and skills they possess, which ultimately regulates their mathematics performance.

Parents' attitudes toward mathematics

Parents' opinions about school, their kids' drive, and their kids' confidence in math all have an effect on how well their kids do in school. Parents who have positive thoughts and support may help their kids become more curious and stronger. On the other hand, parents who have negative thoughts may make their kids afraid of math and less successful. It's important to know what parents think if you want to know how family life affects students' interest in and success in math. This study examines the influence of parents' attitudes towards arithmetic on their children's learning efficacy.

Table 6
Parent Attitude toward Mathematics

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
My child is good at mathematics.	3.12	1.00	N	3.96	0.75	A
The challenge of mathematics problems appeals to my child.	3.14	1.13	N	4.02	0.68	A
Mathematics is hard for my child, even when he/she studies.	3.42	1.01	A	2.56	0.81	D
My child likes solving mathematics problems.	3.46	0.97	A	3.98	0.74	A
My child does not have much interest in mathematics.	3.40	0.99	N	2.02	0.68	D
My child looks forward to mathematics class.	3.20	0.97	N	4.02	0.74	A
My child would like to study mathematics in more detail than he/she does now.	3.22	0.86	N	3.94	0.68	A
My child enjoys discussing mathematics problems.	3.20	0.81	N	3.74	0.83	A
Answering questions in mathematics class makes my child nervous.	4.00	0.70	A	2.26	1.12	D

When my child can't immediately solve a mathematics problem, he/she sticks with it until a solution is reached.	3.48	0.74	A	3.54	0.95	A
My child would rather have someone give him/her the solution to a difficult mathematics problem than have to work it out for himself/herself.	3.60	0.90	A	3.76	0.96	A
My child will need mathematics for his/her future career.	3.72	0.73	A	4.10	0.58	A
My child believes that mathematics is useful in everyday life.	3.90	0.58	A	4.22	0.58	SA
Knowing mathematics will help my child be successful in life.	3.82	0.60	A	4.10	0.81	A
My child frequently uses a calculator for calculations in everyday life.	2.86	0.93	N	3.86	0.61	A
Factor Mean	3.44	0.86	Positive	3.61	0.77	Positive

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree; 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree; 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral; 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree; and 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree.

This portion shows the results of the parents' attitudes toward mathematics among the respondents. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.44 in the low-performing class, about 3.61 in the high-performing class, and an overall standard deviation of 0.86 in the low-performing class and about 0.77 in the high-performing class. This means that the respondents interpreted the parent attitude toward mathematics as positive in both low- and high-performing classes. The data suggests that parents' attitudes toward their children's mathematics vary, and respondents have improved in some way in the low and high-performing classes. The nature of the respondents' parental attitudes toward mathematics can be considered one of the reasons for better performance in mathematics.

This section shows the results of the collected data on parent attitudes towards mathematics. Generally, the overall factor mean and its standard deviation are positive, which means that the parents had better attitudes toward their children's confidence in learning mathematics. Although the subject is so complex, students still find a way to learn mathematics. Therefore, it is important to increase students' confidence in learning the subject so that they also improve their attitude towards it. Teachers need to find strategies to increase students' confidence in learning the subject.

In the study of Mohamed and Waheed (2018), they said that "assessing the perceptions of the respondents on the value of math in their lives exhibits their attitudes towards the subject." This indicates that the respondents had positive attitudes towards the value of mathematics. Students expressed that mathematics is important in their lives because they can integrate these concepts into some of their daily activities. However, these positive attitudes still need to be boosted to make them comprehend that mathematics is beneficial regardless of a person's status in life. Therefore, learning mathematics is important, as it is one of the necessary skills that everyone needs in their lives now and in the future.

Learning Environments in Mathematics

It is revealed that the learning environment has a positive influence on learning achievement. Motivation is a state inherent in a person that inspires him to perform certain actions to accomplish goals. Students who do not know about the purpose of learning in school will certainly disturb their motivation to study.

Table 7
Learning Environment in Mathematics

Indicators	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Mean	SD	DE	Mean	SD	DE
Create safe learning environments to enhance learning through consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures.	4.08	0.78	A	4.22	0.65	SA
Maintain learning environments that promote fairness, respect and care to encourage learning.	3.92	0.7	A	4.12	0.72	A
Manage classroom structure to engage students individually or in groups in exploration, discovery, and meaningful hands-on activities in a variety of physical learning settings.	3.98	0.77	A	4.26	0.78	SA
Maintain supportive learning environments that encourage and inspire students to participate, cooperate and collaborate in lifelong learning.	3.84	0.79	A	3.72	0.86	A
Lead and empower colleagues in promoting learning environments that effectively motivate learners to achieve quality outcomes by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	3.64	0.78	A	4.06	0.74	A
Factor Mean	3.89	0.76	Positive	4.08	0.75	Positive

Note. DE is Descriptive Equivalent. 1.00 to 1.80 is Strongly Disagree; 1.81 to 2.60 is Disagree; 2.61 to 3.40 is Neutral; 3.41 to 4.20 is Agree; 4.21 to 5.00 is Strongly Agree.

This part shows the results of the respondents' learning environment in mathematics. The table shows the overall factor mean of 3.89 in the low-performing class and about 4.08 in the high-performing class, with an overall standard deviation of 0.76 in the low performing class and about 0.75 in the high-performing class. This means that the respondents interpreted the learning environment in both low- and high-performing classes as positive. The data suggests that the respondents' learning environment has improved in some way for all respondents. Given the type of learning environment the respondents have, this can be considered as one of the reasons for the respondents' better performance in mathematics.

Therefore, the learning environment factor influences the success of the learning process. According to F. Rohman (2018), the learning environment is everything that surrounds students when doing learning activities. A conducive learning environment certainly creates a comfortable atmosphere for learning (Arianti, 2019). Supportive learning environment conditions such as the availability of physical learning facilities, a comfortable place to study, a calm environment, and harmonious relationships with the social environment can inspire students to learn mathematics, so that students' achievement in mathematics learning increases.

Summarized Data on the Status of the Respondents in Mathematics

This part shows the outcomes of the summarized data on the status of the respondents in mathematics. The table shows the overall factor mean and its standard deviation of study habits, learning problems, mathematics anxiety, relationships with teachers, parental attitudes, and learning environments for low- and high-performing classes.

Table 8
Summarized Data on the Status of the Respondents in Mathematics

Variables	Low Performing Students (n = 50)			High Performing Students (n = 50)		
	Factor Mean	SD	DE	Factor Mean	SD	DE
Study Habits	3.05	1.08	Satisfactory	4.17	0.85	Very Satisfactory
Learning Problem	3.20	1.04	High	3.42	0.71	Moderate
Mathematics Anxiety	3.60	0.86	Low	4.09	0.84	Low
Teacher relationship	3.96	0.63	Positive	4.05	0.63	Positive
Parent Attitude	3.44	0.86	Positive	3.61	0.77	Positive
Learning Environment	3.89	0.76	Positive	4.08	0.75	Positive

The value of the data collected had the highest factor mean of 3.96 in low-performing classes, that is, the teacher relationship, with a standard deviation of 0.63, which means that students had a positive attitude towards the value of mathematics in their lives with the help and feedback of their teachers. On the other hand, the highest factor mean of 4.17 in high-performing classes could be explained by their attitude and motivation towards the subject, which showed that the respondents were oriented towards learning the subject. is in study habits, with a standard deviation of 0.85, which means that students had very satisfactory scores about the value of mathematics in their lives in an academic sense. Thus, this performance could be explained by their attitude and motivation towards the subject, which showed that the respondents were oriented towards learning the subject. It implies the guidance of teachers to improve their academic attitude towards the subject.

The data suggest that the first two factors have their level of difficulty in learning mathematics. In study habits, both performing classes are satisfactory and very satisfactory, respectively, which means that the learning process is better in high-performing classes compared with low-performing classes. In learning problems, the low-performing students encountered more learning gaps in mathematics than the high-performing students. In mathematics anxiety, both types of respondents have a low level of mathematics performance, which means that the respondents are pressured with the subject but the level of anxiety in mathematics is not high. Moreover, the rest of the factors, such as teacher relationship, parent attitude, and learning environment, are positive, which means that these types of factors exist in learning mathematics for both low and high performers.

Reyes (2015) stated that the students moderately felt test anxiety in mathematics. Test anxiety is considered a factor that might affect the students' mathematics performance. Moreover, teachers may develop different learning strategies in all mathematics subjects. One of the learning outcomes that should be essential for students to achieve their academic goals is the ability to integrate mathematics and science knowledge to solve problems.

Table 9
Significant Analysis on the Six Variables

Variables (Equal Variance Assumed)	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Interpretation
Study habits	-3.90	98.00	0.000	-5.220	1.338	Significant
Learning Problem	-2.63	98.00	0.010	-3.200	1.215	Significant
Mathematics Anxiety	-6.09	98.00	0.000	-4.900	0.805	Significant
Teacher Relations	-1.80	98.00	0.076	-1.400	0.779	Not Significant
Parental Attitudes	-1.81	98.00	0.073	-2.540	1.401	Not Significant
Learning Environment	-1.95	98.00	0.054	-0.920	0.471	Not Significant

Table 9 shows the significant analysis of the six variables of the respondents in the survey concerning the standardized questionnaire with 100 respondents from the low- and high-performing classes. It found that there is no significant difference in teacher relations, parental attitudes, or learning environment with t-values of -1.80, -1.81, and -1.95, respectively. Moreover, there is a significant difference in study habits, learning problems, and mathematics anxiety, with t-values of -3.90, -2.63, and -6.09, respectively.

Guinocor, et al (2020) stated that the college students should develop an effective system of study strategies that will enable them to understand mathematics better and, at the same time achieving more towards their academic performance.

Conclusions

The positive learning insights brought about by the significant analysis of the low- and high-performing classes somehow enable this study to provide another window of opportunity for addressing learning gaps within the context of curricular implementation and reinforcement. With appropriate learning materials, primarily the mathematics enhancement activities, mathematics instruction is always fun and challenging, as learning becomes more valuable not only to teachers but to the learners as well. The mathematics enhancement activities and strategies, being the key output of this study, somehow make mathematics instruction more innovative, engaging, and meaningful, as everyone is given the leverage to benchmark and pilot appropriate and effective pedagogical approaches and strategies as far as the real intent of the implemented curriculum, which is to reinforce weak areas to attain mastery of skills and competencies.

MATHEMATICS ENHANCEMENT PLAN

Mathematics is essential for everyday life—for understanding and engaging with our world. The rationale of the mathematics enhancement plan is that it will enable the development of the learners’ natural ability to think logically and apply the learned competencies to real-life problems. The enhancement plan aims to: (1) enable the learners to have a clear understanding and comprehension of the concepts of mathematics and its applications to real-life settings; (2) provide opportunities that enable the learners to exercise, practice, and discipline mental faculties; (3) enable the learners to appreciate the role of mathematics in the culture of the past and that it continues to play in the present world; and (4) develop in the learners the awareness of mathematics to understand and participate in the general, social, and economic life of the community.

The enhancement activities that can be designed based on the findings of the study are peer tutorials, small or large study groups, integrated seminars or webinars, and mathematics conferences. Furthermore, the enhancement activities can be deployed into the following: (1) make conceptual understanding a priority – a deep understanding of mathematics itself such as the use of visual strategies, schema approach, and unlocking vocabulary words in mathematics; (2) set meaningful homework that builds on class learning – so that the learners will be prepared for the next lesson; (3) use cooperative learning strategies – because it will encourage the learners to express their logical thinking, effective communication, and solves challenging real- world problems; (4) use strategic questioning – to have a deep learning experience into more challenging territory; (5) focus on real problem – solving and reasoning – the most effective instruction equips learners with the problem – solving and reasoning skills they’ll need for real life. And (6) use mixed modes of assessment.

The resources that will be needed in the successful deployment of mathematics for the learners include mathematics exhibits like projects and portfolios created and crafted by the learners, online resources such as PDFs and other Google sites, paper-based resources such as worksheets and quizzes, and technology resources. Nowadays, very famous and somehow effective resources are Zoom or Google Meet for the deployment of class discussions and instructions, Quizlet, and other tech apps for assessment-related activities.

These will enhance the learners, particularly the low-performing ones, so that no learners will be left behind. The peer tutorials and small or large study groups answer the learning problem of the low-performing students because it is an advantage for the high- performing students to approach the low-performing ones to review and tutor lessons in mathematics. The integrated seminars, webinars, and conferences can be done as a culminating activity for the students, in which there are a series of talks and workshops that can monitor the learner’s status towards mathematics. With this, they can transfer their learnings into a real-life setting to maintain the long-term learning process in their grasp.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher formulated the following recommendations:

The students should also study longer than their hobbies to strengthen their understanding of the lesson, be able to ask questions about the solutions that they tackled, and be able to create an application of the lesson in a real-life scenario. Student conferences, seminars, and webinars can be avenues for them to transfer their understanding of the subject.

There should also be an intervention by the parents in helping their children. Learning the subject matter better, like tutorials and other sorts of help in the learning process. Even though they are already in college, always remember that learning has no gender; as long as the learning continues, aid is necessary, especially from the parents.

This research should also be a guiding tool for the teachers who are handling mathematics in the modern world to adjust to the methods and strategies they need to use for guided, interactive, and motivated lessons. Thus, they can utilize learning enhancement programs such as peer mentoring, cooperative learning activities, scaffolding, remediation activities, and other supplementary seminars or webinars that enhance the student’s skills in learning mathematics. By doing so, it will allow the students to be at the center of the teaching and learning process so that the low-performing students can adapt to the modification of the learning process.

REFERENCES

- Acharya, B. R. (2017). Factors affecting difficulties in learning mathematics by mathematics learners. *International Journal of Elementary Education, 6*(2), 8-15.
- Andamon, J. C., & Tan, D. A. (2018). Conceptual understanding, attitude and performance in mathematics of grade 7 students. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research, 7*(8), 96-105.
- Bascones, G. Y., Yunzal, A. N., Jr., & Casinillo, L. F. (2024). Exploring contextual factors affecting student performance in mathematics: A sequential explanatory research. *Canadian Journal of Family and Youth/Le Journal Canadien de Famille et de la Jeunesse, 16*(3), 210-234.
- Byiringiro, E. (2024). Influence of teacher-student relationship on student mathematics achievement in high school in the USA: Mediating roles of students perceptions of mathematics. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences, 2*(1), 375-383.
- Capuno, R., Necesario, R., Etcuban, J. O., Espina, R., Padillo, G., & Manguilimotan, R. (2019). Attitudes, study habits, and academic performance of junior high school students in mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education, 14*(3), 547-561.
- Herges, R. M., Duffied, S., Martin, W., & Wageman, J. (2017). Motivation and achievement of middle school mathematics students. *The Mathematics Educator, 26*(1).
- Kapur, R. (2018). Factors influencing the students' academic performance in secondary schools in India. *University of Delhi, 575-587.
- Lee, Y., Capraro, R. M., & Capraro, M. M. (2018). Mathematics teachers' subject matter knowledge and pedagogical content knowledge in problem posing. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education, 13*(2), 75-90.
- Li, J., & Cai, X.-C. (2024). Domain decomposed classification algorithms based on linear discriminant analysis: An optimality theory and applications. *Neurocomputing, 575*, Article 127261.
- Schulze, S., & Bosman, A. (2018). Learning style preferences and mathematics achievement of secondary school learners. *South African Journal of Education, 38*(1), 1-8.
- Semeraro, C., Giofrè, D., Coppola, G., Lucangeli, D., & Cassibba, R. (2020). The role of cognitive and non-cognitive factors in mathematics achievement: The importance of the quality of the student-teacher relationship in middle school. *PLoS ONE, 15*(4), Article e0231381.
- Skagerlund, K., Skagenholt, M., & Träff, U. (2024). EXPRESS: Mathematics anxiety and number processing: The link between executive functions, cardinality, and ordinality. *Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17470218241234041>
- Soni, A., & Kumari, S. (2017). The role of parental math anxiety and math attitude in their children's math achievement. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education, 15*(2), 331-347.